

Effect of Substituent on Ionisation of Saturated Fatty Acids

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The length of the carbon chain of a fatty acid molecule has been found to have little effect on the ionisation of the un-substituted acid. Decided changes in pK values are observed when a substituent is introduced into the molecule. The manner in which the magnitudes of the ionisation constants of the mono-substituted acids depend on the distances of the substituent-linking C atoms from the carboxyl-carbon atom has been explained from theoretical considerations.

Ionisation capacity of the unsubstituted and the substituted acids and their relative magnitudes were discussed by Wogscheider¹, Derick², MacInnes³, and Langmuir⁴. The effect of dipole moment on dissociation and orientation of organic compounds was discussed by Smallwood⁵. The empirical relation according to Derick² is

$$\left(\frac{\log K_o}{\log K_\alpha} - 1 \right) : \left(\frac{\log K_o}{\log K_\beta} - 1 \right) : \left(\frac{\log K_o}{\log K_\gamma} - 1 \right) = 1 : 1/3 : 1/9$$

and the one due to MacInnes is

$$pK = pK_o - S/d$$

in which the K terms with the subscripts represent the dissociation constants of the un-substituted and the corresponding mono-substituted acids. In the latter, S is a constant with d taking consecutive values from 1 to 4 for α -, β -, γ -, and δ -substituted acids. X-ray investigations^{6,7} reveal that the carbon atoms in fatty acids, hydrocarbons, and ethyl esters are disposed in a zigzag chain, each consecutive three carbons being inclined at an angle of $109^\circ 28'$. From this inclination value and the magnitude of the diameter of the carbon atom, viz., $1.54 \text{ \AA}$, as found in diamond, the linear distances between the carboxyl-C atom, on the one hand, and α -, β -, γ -, δ -, and ϵ -carbon atoms, on the other, can be calculated. The values are 1.54, 2.52, 3.88, 5.04, and $6.36 \text{ \AA}$ respectively. These distances will henceforward be denoted by α , β , γ , δ , and ϵ (Fig. 1A).

Introduction of a negative substituent at, say, α -carbon atom of a fatty acid imparts an additional electric moment to the substituent-linking unit, which eventually leads to a greater ionisation. To calculate the quantitative effect of the additional link moment on

1. *Monatsh.*, 1902, 23, 287.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 33, 1152.
3. *Ibid.*, 1928, 50, 2587.
4. *Chem. Rev.*; 1929, 6, 465.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 3048.
6. Muller and Shearor, *ibid.*, 1923, 45, 2043.
7. Malkin *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1931, 53, 2790.

ionisation, the existence of an imaginary electric dipole at the substituent-linking carbon unit with a moment value μ_s equal to the additional link moment may be assumed.

FIG. 1A

The standard free-energy change ($-\Delta F'_s$) for the ionisation of the substituted acid (the subscript 's' standing for α -, β -, γ -, δ -, etc. substituted) may be deemed to be made up of two parts—one part being the standard free-energy decrease ($-\Delta F^\circ$), associated with the ionisation of the unsubstituted acid, and the other being the potential energy of interaction ($-\Delta F'_s$) between the negatively charged carboxyl group and the assumed equivalent dipole at the substituent-linking unit. The latter energy of interaction may be regarded as equal to the free-energy difference, accounting for the different ionisation capacity of a substituted and the corresponding unsubstituted acids. Viewed from this angle, the standard free-energy change, associated with the ionisation of a single molecule of any s-substituted fatty acid, is

$$-\Delta F'_s = -\Delta F^\circ - \Delta F'_s \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $-\Delta F'_s$ is the potential energy of interaction between the negatively charged carboxyl group and the assumed dipole of moment, μ_s , at the s-carbon atom. These considerations, applied to an α -substituted acid, yield from equation (1)

$$kT \ln K_\alpha = kT \ln K_0 - \frac{e\mu_s \cos \Theta_s}{\alpha^2} \left[1 - \frac{3x^2}{8\alpha^2} \right] \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where K terms denote the respective dissociation constants, k is the Boltzmann constant, e is the electronic charge, μ_s and x are the dipole moment and the length of the polar axis of the assumed dipole at the α -carbon atom; Θ_s is the angle subtended between the polar axis and the line joining its centre with the carboxyl-carbon (Fig. 1B); α is the distance between the carboxyl-C and the α -C atoms. If $x \ll \alpha$, equation (2) simplifies to

$$pK_\alpha = pK_0 + \frac{e\mu_\alpha}{2.303 kT \alpha^2} \quad \dots \quad (2a)$$

where $\mu_\alpha = \mu_s \cos \Theta_s = \text{constant}$ for a particular substituent on the α -C atom.

In the case of β -substituted acid, the value of μ_s will be the same for the same substituent, but the value of the corresponding Θ_s , i.e., the angle of orientation of the polar

axis of the equivalent dipole with respect to the carboxyl-C will alter. In this case, since we may regard that the centre of substitution has been shifted through an angle θ_β relative to α -C and the carboxyl-C line, the value of this new orientation should equal to $\theta_\alpha \cos \theta_\beta$. Similar considerations will hold good for the γ - and other substituted acids.

FIG. 1B

Now, if $\theta_\beta, \theta_\gamma, \theta_\delta, \theta_\epsilon$ etc. represent the angles subtended between the line joining the α -C and the carboxyl-C, on the one hand, and, on the other, β -C and carboxyl-C, γ -C and the carboxyl-C, δ -C and the carboxyl-C, ϵ -C and the carboxyl-C lines respectively, the following relations will hold for the substituted acids (vide Fig. 1B).

$$pK_\beta = pK_o + \frac{e\mu_s \cos\theta_\alpha \cos\theta_\beta}{2.303 kT} \times \frac{1}{\beta^2}$$

or

$$pK = pK_o + \frac{e\mu_\alpha}{2.303 kT} \times \frac{1}{\beta^2 / \cos\theta_\beta} \quad \dots \quad 2(b)$$

$$pK_\gamma = pK_o + \frac{e\mu_\alpha}{2.303 kT} \times \frac{1}{\gamma^2 / \cos\theta_\gamma} \quad \dots \quad 2(c)$$

$$pK_\delta = pK_o + \frac{e\mu_\alpha}{2.303 kT} \times \frac{1}{\delta^2 / \cos\theta_\delta} \quad \dots \quad (2(d))$$

In general, the pK value of a substituted fatty acid is

$$pK_s = pK_o + \frac{e\mu_\alpha}{2.303 kT} \times \frac{1}{l^2 / \cos\theta_L} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where l is the distance of the substituent-linking carbon atom from carboxyl-C atom and θ_L , the angle between the line joining the α -C and the carboxyl-C atoms and the line joining the substituent-linking C atom and the carboxyl-C atom. In Table I, the values of $\theta_\alpha, \theta_\beta, \theta_\gamma$ etc., computed on the basis of zigzag carbon chain in the aliphatic acids, are recorded with the corresponding values of $l^2 / \cos\theta_L$

TABLE I

Angle.	Measure.	$(l^2 / \cos\theta_L) \times 10^{16}$.	Angle.	Measure.	$(l^2 / \cos\theta_L) \times 10^{16}$
θ_α	0.000°	2.37	θ_ϵ	27.26°	45.51
θ_β	35.06°	7.74	θ	35.06°	69.69
θ_γ	22.36°	16.26	θ_ζ	29.96°	90.62
θ_δ	35.06°	30.97	θ_h	35.06°	129.90

Substitution of the specific values of ϵ , k , l^2 , Θ_L and $T = 25^\circ$ in eq. (3) yields the following:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} pK_\alpha &= pK_0 - C\mu_\alpha / 2.37 \\ pK_\beta &= pK_0 - C\mu_\alpha / 7.74 \\ pK_\gamma &= pK_0 - C\mu_\alpha / 16.28 \\ pK_\delta &= pK_0 - C\mu_\alpha / 30.97 \end{aligned} \right\} \dots \quad (4)$$

where $C = 5.067 \times 10^{19}$.

The test of equation (4) may now be made with the set of the available experimental data⁸. The above relation predicts a linear dependence of the pK values of the substituted acids on the reciprocals of the corresponding distances, viz., 2.37, 7.74, 16.28, 30.97, etc. This aspect is realised experimentally when the pK values of a mono-substituted acid for a particular substituent (chloro, bromo, iodo, hydroxy, amino) are plotted (Fig. 2). But unlike MacInnes' relation⁸, the distance ratio comes out to be 0.3:1:2:4:8 approximately for α -, β -, γ -, δ -, and ϵ -substituted acids.

FIG. 2

Fig. 2 shows that in all cases the intercept on the pK axis, providing the pK_0 values, is nearly 4.8. The plot for the amino-substituted acids leads to a somewhat lower value,

8, MacInnes, "Principles of Electrochemistry", 1961, p. 391.

viz., 4.4. The pK_{α} value, obtained according to equation (4), thus coincides closely with those observed experimentally with the unsubstituted saturated acids, irrespective of their chain length.

The gradients of the different curves are found to be -4.5 for chloro and bromo substitutions, -4.66 for amino substitution, -4.125 for iodo, and -2.25 for the hydroxy substitutions. These gradient values may be used in conjunction with equation (3) to obtain the multiplicative factors, with which the ionisation constant of the unsubstituted acid should be multiplied to yield K values of the corresponding substituted acids. For instance, for the chloro-acid, there results from equation (3):

$$\log (K_s/K_0) = \frac{4.5 \cos \theta_L}{l^2}$$

$$\therefore K_s = K_0 \times 10^{4.5 \cos \theta_L / l^2}$$

The values of $10^{4.5 \cos \theta_L / l^2}$ for α -, β -, γ -, and δ -chloro and-bromo acids are 79.3, 3.8, 1.89, and 1.39 as against Wegscheider's empirical figures¹: 90, 6.2, 2.0, 1.3 respectively.

Experimental data⁹ on *n*-butyric acid and monochlorobutyric acids and the figures obtainable from equation (3) for chloro-substitution are recorded in columns 2 and 3 of Table II.

Similar comparative figures, obtained in pursuance of Derick's relation², appear in columns 4 and 5 of the same table. These calculations can be extended to other systems, if desired.

TABLE II

Substituted butyric acid.	K value		$(\frac{\log K_0}{\log K_\alpha} - 1) : (\frac{\log K_0}{\log K_\beta} - 1) : (\frac{\log K_0}{\log K_\gamma} - 1)$	
	Obs.	Calc.	Observed.	Calculated.
-Chloro-	1.39×10^{-3}	1.22×10^{-3}		
β -Chloro-	8.9×10^{-5}	5.9×10^{-5}	1 : 1/3.7 : 1/10.4	1 : 1/4.7 : 1/10.7
γ -Chloro-	3.0×10^{-5}	2.93×10^{-5}		

It should be pointed out that equations (3) and (4) are based on the following approximations:

- (i) The zigzag chain retains the form in solution.
- (ii) The distance of the carboxyl ion from the centre of the polar axis of the assumed dipole has been taken to be α , β , γ , etc. in the respective cases in the computation of the interaction effect between the dipole and the ion,
- (iii) x has been taken to be negligibly small compared to α in framing equation (2).

The last approximation can, however, be removed by taking $x \approx \alpha$, so that the factor $\left(1 - \frac{3x^2}{8\alpha^2}\right)$ would be roughly 5/8. This factor, if taken into consideration, would not impair the linearity demanded by equations (3) and (4) and the general nature of the results will also be similar to those described before.

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Received January 7, 1964.